

Research

Numerical Analysis on Cooling Fan Characteristics

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Abstract: A trial and a numerical examination were led to think about the stream fields of an upgraded hub fan dependent on a business accessible pivotal fan. The PIV estimations showed the external stream field of the hub fan and gave a decent understanding with the 3-D numerical outcomes by subjective and quantitative approvals. Prompt static weight arrangements on the pivoting cutting edges and the streamline examples situated in the rotor part delineated the subtleties of stream qualities in the inward locale of the hub fan, which were accepted to have cozy association with the streamlined clamor age. The time averaged speed and weight arrangements on the estimating plane among rotor and stator uncovered the clamor radiation related with the turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) dispersions just as weight variances prompted by the rotor-stator collaboration. The wind current speed dispersions close to the fan outlet were likewise acquired to break down the blockage impact brought about by the wire direction channel.

Keywords: Numerical Analysis, Cooling Fan

Introduction

As the measure of warmth created from CPUs, realistic cards and different parts in present day PCs has constantly expanded, which has just turned into a difficult issue for the further advancement of PCs. So as to locate a financial and productive approach to comprehend this issue, little size or small hub fans are generally utilized for cooling applications to secure the PC parts overheating and guarantee them working inside a proper temperature go. Be that as it may, the size of pivotal fans is constantly limited by the gather space for ventilation in such hardware. Thus, expanding the rotational speed of the fan is taken as the standard method to upgrade the cooling capacity. Despite the fact that the high rotational speed could tackle the cooling issue, it would likewise cause the significant levels of commotion at the same time. The uproarious condition

would hurt human's wellbeing and furthermore essentially decline the working productivity, so there is a solid interest to decrease the clamor level of cooling fans, and in the interim, keeping up their cooling capacity. The commotion sources in hub fans can be sorted into the mechanical and the aeroacoustic commotion, individually (Nashimoto et al., 2004). While the aeroacoustic clamor will become the overwhelming source when the rotational speed of hub fans continues expanding, so the mechanical commotion source can be ignored. In any case, the elevated level commotion in some pivotal fans is because of the poor structure plan, which would crumble the stream execution just as create superfluous commotion parts. Subsequently, the aeroacoustics levels are to a great extent relied upon the streamlined presentation of the hub fans. In the event that the hub fans' streamlined execution can be enhanced at that point, the aeroacoustic commotion might be basically discouraged. In the previous two decades, widely exploratory and numerical examinations have been done to get the stream fields for further improvement of pivotal fans. Fukano et al. (2004) utilized two hot-wire tests pivoting with the fan sharp edges to gauge the tip leeway stream in an pivotal fan. The outcomes represented that the discrete recurrence commotion was expected to the occasional speed variance in the sharp edge section. Hurault et al., (2012) acquired the consistent and insecure divider weight changes in a pivotal car cooling fan to foresee the flowinduced commotion by using weight sensors. As PIV method has been developed into an successful apparatus in stream field estimations, an enormous number of examinations were executed by utilizing this system in the pivotal fan concentrates to accomplish 2D and stereoscopic speed fields (Estevadeordal et al., 2000; Yoon et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2007). The stream measurements, for example, wake structures, vortices, can be exactly described by estimating the stream fields. Be that as it may, the deficiencies of test examinations are high-venture and extensive stretch when individuals attempt to improve pivotal fans. As of late, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) apparatuses give another ground-breaking and financial approach to get more intricate stream subtleties than test estimations (Gue et al., 2012; Heo et al., 2011; Anup et al., 2014). Hase et al. (2011) utilized a 3-D insecure Reynolds-arrived at the midpoint of Navier-Stokes (URANS) model to assess the broadband clamor of an hub fan as far as the tempestuous dynamic vitality (TKE) dispersions. Liu et al. (2014) conveyed out a numerical report to explore the precarious stream qualities initiated by the rotorstator connection. It was discovered that the weight vacillations and stator lean points could be the fundamental hotspots for the connection clamor.

An ever increasing number of analysts like to receive a consolidated technique (test and reproduction) to direct the investigation on hub fan since it can abbreviate the time and abatement the speculation and it has just been shown as a proficient path in numerous applications. Jiang et al. (2007) did a thorough perception of a hub fan stream field by CFD recreation, the tip vortex was found to assume a significant job in the blockage impact in the stream, which additionally furnished a decent concurrence with Fukano's model for trial examination. Hurault et al. (2010) led a computation by contrasting the compass impact between the numerical and trial arrangements. The outcomes demonstrated that the TKE could be a very significant parameter to anticipate the transmitted clamor in turbomachinery, and the outspread speed segment ought to likewise be dissected because of the spiral harmony speculation which is regularly wrongly expected.

In the present examination, a trial and a numerical report were led to research the point by point stream fields of a recently planned pivotal fan dependent on a monetarily accessible item. A computerized Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) framework was utilized to lead the external stream field estimations to measure violent stream structures around the pivotal fan and furthermore give the approval to the reproduction results. A CFD work was used to acquire the inward stream amounts, for example, TKE, streamline and weight vacillations inside the hub fan for further investigation relevant to the aeroacoustics and streamlining.

Experimental Setup

The axial fan model

Fig. 1: Axial fan model

Figure 1 illustrates the configurations of the optimized axial fan model. It should be noted that this fan was modified based on a commercially-available axial fan. The detailed modifications of this fan in comparison to the baseline fan can be found in the previous study (Wang et al., 2014). Except the motor, all the other components in this fan were redesigned in order to achieve better flow and acoustic performance. The axial fan was made of plastics and precisely manufactured by a rapid prototyping machine.

PIV measurements

Fig. 2: PIV measurement set-up

In the present examination, a high-goals advanced PIV framework was utilized to catch the wholefield stream subtleties around the pivotal fan models (appeared in Fig. 2) and give a sensible approval for the numerical reproduction. During the PIV estimations, the wind current was seeded with $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ oil beads by utilizing a haze machine (ROSCO 1900). Light was given by a twofold beat recurrence multiplied Nd:YAG laser (EverGreen 200) with a heartbeat vitality of 200 mJ at the wavelength of 532 nm. The laser pillar was molded into a sheet by a set of mirrors alongside round and barrel shaped focal points. The thickness of the laser sheet in the estimation district was around 1 mm. A high-goals 14-piece CCD camera (PCO1600) was utilized for picture procurement with the hub of camera situated opposite to the laser sheet. The CCD camera and the twofold beat Nd:YAG laser were associated with a host PC through advanced defer generator

(BNC565), which controlled the planning of the laser brightening and camera procurement. In this investigation, the fan was worked at the stream pace of 5m³/min, which speaks to the regular working condition. For each tried case, 600 momentary casings were caught for post-preparing. After PIV picture securing, the prompt PIV speed vectors were acquired from the cross-connection with 32 × 32 pixels cross examination windows. A compelling cover of half of the cross examination windows was utilized in the PIV picture preparing. The dispersions of the troupe found the middle value of stream amounts were determined from the information after picture preparing.

Numerical methods

The PIV measurements only provide the flow details outside of the axial fan, but the flow statistics inside the fan are more important to give a further understanding for the noise radiation. However, due to the complicated geometry of the axial fan, it is difficult to visualize the internal flow field of the axial fan by using PIV technique. Hence, numerical method would be a more realistic way to get an insight into the flow structures in the fan model. In the present study, the 3D URANS (Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes) model was implemented through the commercially-available solver, ANSYS/FLUENT to simulate the flow field of the axial fan. URANS model is an economic and effective tool that offers reasonable results, which was widely used in the investigations of axial fan studies (Akturk et al., 2009).

Governing equations

The fluid dynamics in the present axial fan is an incompressible, three-dimensional and fully turbulent flow, which is generally expressed by the Navier-Stokes equations in Cartesian tensor notation as follows:

Continuity

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Momentum

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i u_j - \tau_{ij})}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + S_i \quad (2)$$

where u_i and u_j are the velocity components of the air flow, ρ is the air density, p is the pressure, τ_{ij} is the Reynolds stress component and S_i is the momentum source.

Computational domain and mesh generation

Figure 3(a) demonstrates the computational space for the mimicked hub fan model. All together to limit the impacts from the limit, the delta and outlet limits were stretched out to 5D and 8D away from the fan, individually. Figure 3(b) outlines the work utilized for the present figuring. In light of the confounded edge geometry, the unstructured work was utilized and crystal layers were additionally adjusted close to the divider to improve the precision of the stream field. The remainder of districts in the figuring area were produced with fine auxiliary cross sections to decrease the planning and lift the accuracy of estimation. Figure 4 delineates the matrix autonomy study by utilizing the region weighted normal complete weight on the stator outlet under various cell sizes. It tends to be unmistakably observed that the all out weight would increment along the work number increments. In any case, when the quantity of cells was over 3.5 million, the all out weight progressed toward becoming leveled off. Along these lines, 3.5 Millions cells were utilized in this investigation, which would be a sensible work size to unite all the stream amounts for economy also, exactness.

(a) Computational domain

(b) Mesh used in the calculation

Fig. 3: Computational domain and mesh

Fig. 4: Grid independence study

Results and Discussions

The PIV estimation got the external outfit found the middle value of speed fields of the test fan, which can likewise offer a bona fide approval for the computational arrangements and give a supplement for the recreated outcomes. It ought to be noticed that the hub fan was worked at the equivalent rotational speed during the PIV estimations and reproductions, and the computational model was a full scale three-dimensional stream fields and no rearrangements was expected.

Fig. 5: Ensemble-averaged velocity distributions on the same measuring plane from

experiment (left) and simulation (right)

Fig. 6: Ensemble-averaged streamwise velocity profiles

Figure 5 represents the group found the middle value of speed correlations between the test results and the numerical arrangements at a similar 2-D focal estimation plane. The stream structures and the forms of the speed greatness, got from the computational arrangements coordinate very well with the test results. There is a distribution area, to be specific, low-energy wind stream locale for them two happens close the engine area because of high speed slope existing in the shear layer. this wonder was additionally outlined in Yoon et al's. (2004) work when they researched a low-speed pivotal fan by utilizing a stereoscopic PIV estimation. The low-force wind stream locale is tilted upward around 7 deg in the wake of the test case, yet the tilted point is seen as it were around 2 deg in the reenactment case. The extension plot for the upper stream in the trial results is around 25 deg in contrast with a littler point of 21 deg in the reenactment arrangements, yet the lower stream in the reproduction arrangement demonstrates a bigger tilted edge than that of the exploratory outcomes. So as to quantitatively look at the speed fields between the exploratory and numerical arrangements, the transverse speed profiles at three areas (i.e., $X/D=-0.5, X/D=0.5$ and $X/D=1.0$) were extricated from the PIV results and reenactments. Figure 6 exhibits the transverse speed circulations on the estimating areas. The speed is standardized by the found the middle value of speed U_{avg} that is determined by the stream rate partitioned by the stream section zone of the hub fan ($U_{avg}=Q/A_n$) in the stream entry. As appeared in the plot, the determined speed appropriations at $X/D=-0.5$, which speaks to the area before the fan delta, concurs very well with that from the trial results. Just a little disparity exists on the speed pinnacle esteems. The speed conveyances on the lower stream and focal district behind the rotor in the numerical reenactments

coordinate pleasantly with the test results at the area of $X/D=0.5$. A slight over-expectation for the wind stream width is found in the upper stream of the mimicked outcomes. In any case, the speed conveyance at the situation of $X/D=1.0$ doesn't demonstrate a comparative pattern as the past two areas. An auxiliary speed peak is seen in the lower stream through the examination which is missing from the reproduction results. By and large, it very well may be inferred that the width and stream structures in the wakes between examination and count are inside a sensible range for forecast, and this quantitative correlation can offer the certainty for breaking down the stream fields precisely inside the pivotal fan.

Figs.5 and 6 have showed the outer flow fields of the axial fan, but the internal flow of the axial fan, which contributes the main aeroacoustic source such as the tip leakage vortex and the passage vortex (Lu et al., 2007) and rotor-stator interaction (Laurent et al., 2011), still hasn't uncovered in relation to the noise generation. Hence, the inner flow fields should be achieved for further analysis due to its importance on the aeroacoustics of the axial fan. Figure 7 illustrates the instantaneous pressure coefficient distributions on the suction surface of the rotating blades in one revolution with a phase angle interval of 60 degrees. In the present simulation, there are 7 identical blades that would rotate in anticlockwise direction, and the blade position shown in Fig. 7(a) is identified as the initial phase angle (i.e., Phase angle = 0 deg). As expected, it can be easily found that the high negative pressure regions appear close to the blade tip, which indicates that the air flow is accelerated to the highest level in rotary region. However, the static pressure on the blade surface increases gradually towards the trailing edge of the blade, which can be inferred as a suppression of airflow along the streamwise. This could be induced by the tip vortex that plays a major role in the flow fields near the blade tip (Jiang et al., 2007), and has a large blockage effect to the airflow. As mentioned above, the flow field in the stator cannot be treated as an axial-symmetric since wires extruded from the rotor part to the fan casing. When the blade rotates closer to guide channel, the static pressure near the tip region is increased to some extent compared with the blade on other phase angles, which can be inferred that the airflow is restricted by the blocking effect of the guide channel. However, there is no significant effect on the static pressure distributions near the blade trailing edge caused by the stators in comparison to Lu et al.'s (2007) findings, as more stator struts can decrease the instantaneous pressure fluctuations due to relative motion between rotor and stator.

Fig. 7: Instantaneous static pressure coefficient distributions on the blade suction surface. (a) Phase angle = 0deg, (b) Phase angle = 60deg, (c) Phase angle = 120deg, (d) Phase angle = 180deg, (e) Phase angle = 240deg, (f) Phase angle = 300deg.

In order to capture the flow characteristics inside the axial fan, three planes, as shown in Fig. 8, were extracted from the numerical solutions for revealing a detailed investigation. Plane #1 was selected right in the rotary region and plane #2 was arranged between the rotor and stator where could reveal the severe interactions caused by the rotating blades and the stationary guide vanes. Plane #3 was selected to reflect the downstream flow fields at the fan outlet. It should be noted that, since this simulation is an unsteady calculation, the instantaneous flow quantities can be visualized on plane #1 and the time-averaged results can be recorded on plane #2 as well as plane #3.

Fig. 8: Measuring planes

Conclusion

A test and a numerical report were led to examine the stream fields of an advanced hub fan dependent on a business accessible fan. By subjectively contrasting the stream structures and quantitatively looking at the speed circulations, it was discovered that the PIV estimations concurred well with the reproduction arrangements and gave the fundamental certainty for investigating the stream fields inside the hub fan. The prompt weight arrangements spoke to the high negative weight district on the sharp edge surface close to the cutting edge tip, which demonstrated the wind current was quickened to the most elevated level in the rotor locale. When the cutting edge turned nearer to the guide channel, the static weight close to the tip district was expanded somewhat contrasted and the cutting edge on other stage edges.

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